

Mathematical truth from a neutrosophic point of view

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Abstract:

Neutrosophy, a new philosophy deals with neutrality. Neutrosophy states that between an idea $\langle Z \rangle$ and its opposite $\langle \text{Anti-}Z \rangle$, there exists a continuum-power spectrum of neutralities $\langle \text{Neut-}Z \rangle$. In neutrosophy, an idea $\langle Z \rangle$ is $a\%$ true, $b\%$ indeterminate, and $c\%$ false, where the sum of a, b, c lies between 0% to 300% . Neutrosophic logic and neutrosophic set deal with uncertainty comprehensively. Different modes of thinking produce different mathematical patterns. Several studies on mathematical truth were done by the researchers but neutrosophic logic was not employed. The paper deals with the mathematical truth, which is the first study based on neutrosophy that reflects the novelty of the work.

1. Introduction:

What is mathematical truth? Many researchers studied mathematical truth [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. In 1994 Zheng [8] (1994) studied the pattern view theory of mathematics. Zheng [8] presented two types of mathematical truth, namely realistic truth and formal truth. But did not consider the case of uncertainty. To deal with non-stochastic uncertainty, Zadeh [9] grounded the Fuzzy Set (FS) by introducing the Membership Function (MF), and the belongingness of an element is presented by the grade of membership in $[0, 1]$. In 1986, Atanassov [10] grounded the degree of falsity as an independent entity and proposed Intuitionistic FS (IFS). In 1998, Smarandache [11] introduced neutrosophy and grounded Neutrosophic Set (NS) based on neutrosophy. NS [11] is presented by three independent entities, namely, truth MF, indeterminacy MF, and falsity MF such that the sum of their degrees lies in the non-standard interval $]0, 3^*[$ to deal with mathematical

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problems with non-stochastic uncertainty. NSs have been utilized to solve real-world problems in uncertain environments [12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17]. Details of NSs and their applications can be found in [18, 19, 20, 21]. Based on neutrosophy, it can be said that mathematics is capable to handle uncertain, and inconsistent information. In this study, neutrosophy is explored to deal with mathematical truth.

Research gap: Mathematical truth based on neutrosophy is not presented in the literature.

Motivation for the study: We initiate the study to present mathematical truth based on neutrosophy to explore the research gap.

The objective of the study:

- To develop different types of mathematical truth based on neutrosophy.

2. Basics of some theories related to neutrosophy

Florentin Smarandachē, a Romanian- American mathematician introduced neutrosophy [11], a new philosophy in the late 90s.

- **Main Principle [11]**

There exists a continuum-power spectrum of neutralities $\langle \text{Neut-Z} \rangle$ between any idea $\langle Z \rangle$ and its opposite idea $\langle \text{Anti-Z} \rangle$.

- **Fundamental Thesis [11]**

Any idea $\langle Z \rangle$ is $a\%$ true, $b\%$ indeterminate, and $c\%$ false, where $a, b,$ and $c \in]0, 1+[$

- **Neutrosophic Set [11]**

Let U be a space of objects. An NS S on U is defined as:

$$S = \{z, \langle p(z), q(z), r(z) \rangle \mid y \in U\}$$

Where each of $p(z), q(z), r(z): U \rightarrow]0, 1+[$ represents r the degree of truth MF, indeterminacy MF, and falsity MF of an element $z \in U$ to the set S with $0 \leq p(z) + q(z) + r(z) \leq 3^+$.

3. Mathematical truth based on neutrosophy

According to the pattern view theory of mathematics [8], mathematical truth are two types:

- Realistic Truth:** This implies an agreement with reality. If a mathematical theory appears useful in dealing with some aspect of empirical activities, it is said that there exists some realistic truth in it.

(ii) **Formal Truth:** Assume that a mathematical theory emerges from rational creative thinking, which implies that it determines a quantitative pattern. So, the mathematical theory in its direct form refers to the formal truth.

Rational creative thinking means logical construction that should satisfy the conditions of logical consistency.

Fuzzy truth: If a mathematical theory has some degree of truth (lies between 0 and 1), then it is said that there exists some mathematical truth in it (fuzzy mathematical truth)

Intuitionistic fuzzy truth: If a mathematical theory has some degree of truth and some degree of false which are independent of each other such that their sum is less than 1, it is said that there exists some mathematical truth (intuitionistic fuzzy mathematical truth) in it.

Neutrosophic truth:

(i) If a mathematical theory has three parts, namely, degrees of truth, indeterminacy, and falsity MFs respectively, it is said that there exists some neutrosophic truth in it. The sum of degrees lies in $]0, 3+[$. In single valued NS [22], the sum of the degrees lies in $[0, 3]$.

(ii) **Absolute truth:** If a mathematical theory has the highest value 1 as the degree of truth MF, and the minimum values i.e., zeroes as the degrees of indeterminacy, and falsity MFs, then it is absolute truth.

(iii) **Absolute indeterminacy:** If a mathematical theory has the highest value 1 as the degree of indeterminacy MF and the minimum values i.e., zeroes as the degrees of truth and falsity MFs, then it is absolute indeterminacy.

(iii) **Absolute False:** If a mathematical theory has the highest value 1 as the degree of falsity MF, and the minimum values i.e., zeroes, as the degrees of truth and indeterminacy MFs, then it is absolutely false.

Neutrosophic mathematical truth is not arbitrary but is guided by the concepts of neutrosophy.

4. Conclusion :

This study discusses different types of mathematical truths. The concept of mathematical truth is a dynamic process. Different philosophies of mathematics produce different concepts of mathematical truth. This paper presents mathematical truth based on neutrosophy. In the future mathematics education based on neutrosophy can be further explored.

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